

High-Fidelity Multi-Physics Platforms for Pressure Vessel Fluence Calculations: a Comparison with Low-Fidelity Codes

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803303

ABSTRACT

The effective neutron source specified in reactor pressure vessel fluence calculations consist of a pin-wise neutron sampling probability and an assembly-wise emission spectrum. A detailed analysis of the impact of using higher fidelity tools for the determination of the neutron source used in pressurized water reactors (PWR) vessel fluence calculations is one of the research goals of the EURATOM project EVEREST. In this work, two pathways for the definition of the effective neutron source are compared. The first one employs the traditional two-step approach for core follow calculations, i.e. lattice transport followed by full-core diffusion. The higher fidelity alternative consists in full-core transport coupled with sub-channel codes for the thermal-hydraulic solution. The impact of the use of higher-order methods on the calculated fast flux at the reactor pressure vessel varies according to the location of interest; for the beltline location the observed effect remains below 5%. Potentially higher impacts are observed at the top and at the bottom of the active core height, where the effect can reach up to 8%. The radial power distribution tilt observed in low-fidelity solutions with simplified radial reflector modeling is identified as the main contributor to the discussed discrepancy.

Keywords: Multi-Physics, High-Fidelity, PWR, Vessel Fluence, Long Term Operation

1. INTRODUCTION

Reactor pressure vessel (RPV) fluence calculations have been performed successfully for many years in the nuclear industry, targeting mostly high-flux beltline locations (i.e. at core mid-height) and achieving satisfactory results in comparison with available capsule measurements [1]. Fluence calculations normally consist of a two-step procedure. At first an effective neutron source is determined taking into account the actual operational history of the reactor. This means extracting information from core-follow calculations. As a second step, this neutron source is used in shielding calculations meant to calculate the fast neutron flux at the RPV. The determination of an effective neutron source has usually resorted to Low-Fidelity (LF) tools (i.e. lattice codes followed by full-core diffusion) that have historically shown a remarkable performance for core-follow calculations. As the nuclear industry faces the need to prove the feasibility of Long Term Operation (LTO) of nuclear power plants, both the beltline and the regions beyond it (i.e. the so-called extended-beltline locations) become safety relevant because of the accumulated neutron fluence. High-Fidelity (HF) tools could potentially help providing a better quantification of safety margins [2].

Significant effort has been put in the development of HF tools for coupled neutronic/thermal hydraulics (N/TH) calculations. On the neutronic side these efforts have produced neutron transport solvers based on method of characteristics (MOC), discrete ordinates (Sn) and Monte-Carlo (MC) for core follow modeling. On the thermal-hydraulic side, sub-channel codes have shown robustness and speed for PWR

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applications. The coupling of sub-channel codes to full core neutron transport has been successfully achieved in the context of the Consortium for Advanced Simulation of Light Water Reactors (CASL) [3].

To the extent of the authors' knowledge, a systematic analysis of the impact of using higher fidelity tools for the determination of the neutron source used in LWR vessel fluence calculations has not been thoroughly documented. This work aims at presenting the first steps towards the quantification of this HF/LF calculational bias. This research was conducted in the context of the EURATOM project Experiments for Validation and Enhancement of the REactor preSSure vessel fluence assessment (EVEREST), whose over-arching goal is to contribute to the LTO of the existing nuclear fleet. In the following section, the methodologies for LF and HF vessel fluence calculation are presented, together with the strategy for bias investigation.

2. METHODOLOGY

The effective neutron source is specified in shielding calculations in terms of the neutron sampling probability and the emission spectrum. These specifications require knowledge of the local power produced (e.g. the pin power P), the average number of neutrons emitted per fission ν , the energy released per fission E and the fuel composition along the irradiation history of a power plant. The low-fidelity methodologies presented in past and recent literature generally resort to a pin-wise description of the neutron source intensity and an assembly average specification of the emission spectrum χ [1] [4]. Given that LF core simulators do not provide explicit information on ν , E or fuel composition during irradiation, these have to be retrieved from the lattice code simulations. Conversely, if a HF tool is used, both neutron transport and depletion information can be retrieved for each pin from the output of the multi-physics platform. In this regard, Figure 1 shows the two methodologies applied for this study. The SCALE6.3/Polaris-GenPMAXS-PARCS code package was selected as LF scheme, while VERA4.3, consisting of coupled N/TH simulations using MPACT and CTF, was used as HF tool. The illustration highlights quantities of interest and level of detail for the source definition, i.e. assembly-wise or pin-wise specifications. The preparation of the source is handled by the EPFL tool NEUTHOS, which retrieves information of interest from both low and high-fidelity models. The neutron sources are then provided to the Monte-Carlo code Serpent for the shielding calculations. The last step employs the variance reduction (VR) options available in Serpent, tallying the fast flux at the RPV location and targeting a relative statistical error lower than 0.2%.

At a high-level, the fundamental differences between LF and HF methodologies for core follow calculations can be broken down into neutronics, thermal-hydraulics and depletion. For the first, PARCS would perform full core calculations employing nodal diffusion at the assembly level, while pin-power reconstruction schemes are required to obtain the neutron source for each fuel rod. On the contrary, MPACT is a full core neutron transport solver, employing a 2D/1D synthesis consisting of an MOC solution for the 2D radial problem and a 1D axial problem solved by diffusion or SP3. For thermal-hydraulics, PARCS employs a closed-channel 1D mass-energy balance at an assembly level. Conversely, CTF is a sub-channel code, solving eight conservation equations. Three fields are modeled; liquid film, liquid drops and vapour, with the liquid fields sharing an energy equation. CTF provides pin-wise resolution for moderator temperature and density. Finally, PARCS uses macroscopic cross-sections prepared by Polaris/GENPMAXS as a function of burnup (and other state variables) to take into-account the effect of depletion, while VERA (through the ORIGEN code) solves Bateman equations for each pin. The former approach is often referred to as "macroscopic" depletion, the latter as "microscopic".

The quantification of computational biases between LF and HF simulations should be carried out so as to identify, among the discrepancies described above, the main contributors to the final difference in vessel fluence predictions. Following this logic, a 2D case with fixed thermal-hydraulic conditions was targeted at first. The scope was to isolate the effect of 2D MOC applied to the neutron transport problem and compare it with the performance of nodal diffusion. The comparison was then extended to 3D cases, targeting at first a full-core comparison with Serpent and fixed thermal-hydraulic conditions.

Figure 1. LF and HF methodologies for RPV fluence calculation.

This would allow to quantify the effect of the 2D/1D synthesis of MPACT. The analysis was finally extended to 3D cases with feedback, where the comparison with Serpent was not targeted anymore, but the differences between Polaris/PARCS and VERA would be studied. With this scope, VERA was employed both with MPACT internal TH model and with the CTF coupling. The first approach would resemble the mass-energy balance applied by PARCS, the second one would instead be able to show the impact of an advanced feedback treatment. These comparisons included cases where the neutron sources were being produced from a one-statepoint neutron transport/diffusion calculation for a fresh core. In order to complete the investigation of HF/LF computational biases, the effect of the microscopic depletion strategy of MPACT, with Bateman equations being solved after each transport calculation, should be quantified. This goal can be achieved by focusing on a shielding calculation at the end of one operational cycle. The difference between the HF and the LF source here will not be caused only by the pin-power calculation, but also by the isotopic composition influencing the emission spectrum. For this scope, a shielding calculation after 350 days of irradiation was carried out. The full set of simulations performed for this task is summarised in Table I.

Case	Feedback	Depletion	Shielding	Comparison goal
2D	Off	Fresh core	No VR	MOC Transport vs Nodal Diffusion
3D	Off	Fresh core	With VR	2D/1D Synthesis vs Nodal Diffusion
3D	Internal T/H	Fresh core	With VR	1D mass-energy vs MPACT internal TH
3D	Sub-channel	Fresh core	With VR	1D mass-energy vs 3D sub-channel code
3D	Sub-channel	350 EFPD	With VR	Macroscopic vs microscopic depletion

Table I. Strategy and simulations for the investigation of HF/LF biases and their impact on RPV fluence.

The comparison of the low and high-fidelity methodology focused on the Turkey Point 3 reactor (TP3). This Westinghouse 3-loop Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) was the subject of recent validation activi-

ties for the SCALE Polaris/PARCS code package [5]. In order to start with a completely fresh core, the presented analysis targeted the first operational cycle. The core was loaded with four different assembly types, featuring three enrichment levels (1.9%, 2.5% and 3.2%) with a low-non-uniformity pattern (i.e. higher enrichment in the periphery of the core) and Pyrex burnable poison rods. More detailed modeling information are available in the public EPRI report [6]. Figure 2 shows an azimuthal and axial view of the Serpent model, where the axial reflectors are homogenized and simplified to feature only water.

Before concluding on the impact of HF platforms for vessel fluence calculation, the quality of the LF and HF models built for this study should be assessed. For this scope, the Serpent MC model was also used to have a reference full-core solution with pin-wise resolution to compare the cases without feedback.

Figure 2. The Turkey Point 3 reactor Serpent model.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Feedback Off: Investigation of the impact of the diffusion approximation

Figure 3 presents the results of the pin-power LF-HF comparison for the 2D case. The metrics shown consist of the maximum pin-power relative percentage difference (RPD) for each assembly of the TP3 core and the Root Mean Square of the RPD (RMS) for each of these assemblies. Nonetheless, the legend box features the full core RMS and the outer core RMS, the latter referring to those assemblies whose contour in the checkerboard pattern is in bold. The focus on the outer core is justified by the fact that only peripheral assemblies contribute to the vessel fluence, hence an improvement in pin-power calculation there could be very significant for LTO applications. Figure 4 instead shows only the pin-wise RPD for the 3D case with no TH feedback. For a more traditional look at the performance of LF and HF codes, 1D axial, 2D radial, 3D nodal and 3D pin-wise RMS are also reported in Table II for both 2D and 3D cases with no TH feedback. The results show the evident amelioration of the HF tools in predicting pin-powers. For the 2D case, MPACT brings about an improvement of outer core RMS from 4.5% to 1.1%. Previous studies have shown that the performance of higher fidelity tools can be further refined with respect to what obtained in this study. Specifically, achieving 3D Pin RMS around 0.5% is possible, when comparing to a MC solution for which the same cross-section processing tool has been used [7]. On the other hand, the traditional two-step approach has also shown significant improvements, going down to 1.3% in 2D axially-averaged pin-power RMS in recent studies

[8]. This improvement stems, among other modeling practices [9], from a refined treatment of the radial reflectors. The use of a simple 1D reflector model for the Polaris/PARCS simulations is probably one of the most significant culprit for the worse LF performance in this study. This is visible in Figure 3, where the PARCS' results exhibit an evident power tilt and larger discrepancies at the periphery of the core. On the other hand, the novelty of this work does not stem from the pin-power full core comparison discussed here, but rather from the application of the full computational chain needed to estimate vessel fluence from both low and high-fidelity neutron sources, under reasonable modeling practices.

With this in mind, LF and HF neutron sources were produced with NEUTHOS and used in both 2D and 3D Serpent shielding calculations. For the 2D case, the HF source would yield a 4.9% higher fast flux at the RPV. The effect is similar for the 3D case, where the fast flux integrated over the whole surface of the RPV would be 4.4% higher. This seems to confirm what largely expected: the computational bias in the definition of a HF neutron source for vessel fluence calculations is to be attributed to the application of an MOC formulation for the radial neutron transport problem. The differences are further enhanced by the simplified radial reflector adopted for the LF modeling.

Figure 3. Pin power comparison for a 2D case between PARCS, VERA and Serpent (reference).

Geometry	Feedback	1D Axial RMS		2D Radial RMS		3D Nodal RMS		3D Pin RMS	
		P	V	P	V	P	V	P	V
2D	Off	-	-	3.05%	0.76%	-	-	-	-
3D	Off	1.06%	0.37%	4.20%	1.41%	4.35%	1.45%	5.10%	1.75%

Table II. RMS for PARCS (P) and VERA (V) full-core simulations compared to Serpent reference solution.

3.2. Feedback On: Investigation of the impact of high-fidelity TH tools

The neutron source intensity as defined from PARCS and VERA simulations with their internal TH solver is compared with the results of the simulation featuring the highest fidelity, i.e. VERA with CTF. The comparison is shown in Figure 5 where both a 3D view and a 2D midplane cut of the two outermost rings of fuel assemblies are presented. The PARCS performance confirms the pattern seen in the cases

Figure 4. Pin power comparison for a 3D case between PARCS, VERA and Serpent (reference).

with no feedback, with a 3D Pin RMS around 4%. Instead, VERA-ITH overpredicts the source intensity at the bottom and at the top of the core, resulting into an RMS of 1.05%. To complete the presentation of the results of this preliminary investigation, HF/LF biases for 3D cases are summarized in Figure 6 (left), where the ratio of fast flux predicted using neutron sources from VERA and PARCS is shown (V/P ratio). The results are presented for the four 3D cases, considering three different axial locations on the RPV inner surface: the top 30 cm, the beltline and the bottom 30 cm. An additional column, labeled "all", presents the average of the three locations. Feedback appears to generally reduce the differences between the two methodologies, apparently compensating for some of the limitations of two-group diffusion. A detailed comparison of relevant TH quantities will be part of the future studies aimed at a better understanding of the sources of discrepancy between methodologies.

3.3. Depletion On: Investigation of the impact of microscopic depletion

Differences in depletion treatment display a visible impact on fast flux predictions. As illustrated in Figure 6 (left), after 350 days the V/P ratio is approximately 0.97 at both the bottom and top of the core, whereas it remains around 1.03 in the beltline region. The evolution of this bias during irradiation is also displayed in Figure 6 (right): for each of the shown state-points, two shielding calculations are run employing sources from VERA (with CTF) and Polaris/PARCS and accounting for the fuel composition predicted by the two calculation schemes. The V/P ratio is plotted for the four regions, revealing a general trend: the bias appears to decrease over the course of irradiation, possibly as a result of both the saturation of plutonium concentration in the fuel predicted by the two methodologies and the progressive flattening of power profiles with burnup. It should be pointed out that this comparison does not conclude on the quality of macroscopic or microscopic depletion, but rather tries to quantify the potential impact of having to reconstruct the fuel composition from the reference Polaris calculations, rather than being able to access this information directly in the core-follow calculations. This preliminary observation should be complemented by a larger set of state-points, a longer irradiation time and a more in-depth comparison of the predicted fuel composition.

Figure 5. Source intensity comparison for cases with feedback.

Figure 6. Preliminary results of 3D bias investigation for RPV fast flux: V/P ratio for different 3D cases (left), V/P ratio evolution during irradiation (right).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a LF and a HF scheme for vessel fluence calculations are compared. The influence of higher-order methods on the calculated fast flux at the reactor pressure vessel is found to depend on the RPV location considered. In the beltline region, the 2.84% difference obtained for the 3D case with CTF is similar to what observed during the CASL project, when the performance of VERA Ex-Core calculations was compared with legacy results from DORT [10]. The conclusions of this preliminary analysis seem

to suggest that HF codes cannot account for more than 8% difference in fast flux prediction regardless of the tally position on the RPV inner surface and independently from the observed depletion step. The primary source of the observed discrepancies is attributed to the radial power distribution tilt visible in low-fidelity solutions employing simplified radial reflector models. Future work will aim at a better understanding of the sources of these discrepancies and at the application of the same investigation strategy to other reactors with different fuel types, loading patterns and average burnup. The analysis will include multiple cycles, targeting an exhaustive understanding of how HF/LF biases evolve during the operating life of a reactor.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was conducted within European research program EVEREST under grant agreement n° 101163288. The research and publication are co-funded by Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation Grants n° 24.00340.

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